

2

Scientific Forestry and the New Ecological Regime in Colonial India

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Abstract: *Most of the seminal writings on the Environmental History of Colonial and contemporary India have unfurled the mega and micro narratives of forestry in terms of social conflict or ecological enquiry. Forests have been represented as a contested landscape which exists either in harmony or in conflict with the human world. Forest as a socio-ecological domain has been brought to the forefront by the Indian Environmental historians altogether from a different dimension. They have informed how forest is spatially, materially and culturally distinct as source of food, fuel and material shelter. Such seminal discourses provide forest a place of prominence in the contemporary environmental debate.*

The present work examines the colonial notion of ‘conservation’ that shaped the forest management in British India during the 1850s. The idea of conservation was implemented through ‘scientific forestry’, a colonial narrative intricately linked to imperialist narratives emphasising progress and western superiority. It emphasised the preservation and a competent western management of the colony’s forests; however, it effectively converted the forests into valuable commodities, resulting in their systematic depletion.

Keywords: Scientific Forestry, Colonial Forest Management, Continental Tradition, Environment, German School of Forestry

Introduction: Most of the seminal writings on the Environmental History of Colonial and contemporary India have unfurled the mega and micro narratives of forestry in terms of social conflict or ecological enquiry. Forests have been represented as a contested landscape which exists either in harmony or in conflict with the human world. Forest as a socio-ecological domain has been brought to the forefront by the Indian Environmental historians altogether from a different dimension. They have informed how forest is spatially, materially and culturally distinct as source of food, fuel and material shelter. Such seminal discourses provide forest a place of prominence in the contemporary environmental debate.

Forests play an essential role in the protection and maintenance of the natural environment as well as in the evolution of social, cultural, civic and state institutions. Forests provide life support system for civilization to sustain in every phase of history. The colonized Indian forests had undergone massive phenomenal changes and transformation. The colonial power in one form or other started penetrating for the establishment of legal proprietary hold over the forests.

Major Debates on British Forest Policy in India:

The scholarship on India's Environmental History is still in its embryonic stage both in terms of interrogation of facts and finding out new ways of looking into the past. The scholarship is largely divided on the issue of the impact of colonialism on Indian forest resources. The nationalist school has emphasized the pre-colonial notion of 'ecological equilibrium' while the imperial writers have harped on the positive motives. The imperial officers and scholars such as B. Ribbentrop in his Book "Forestry in British India" (Calcutta, 1900, Reprinted by Indus Publishing Company, New Delhi 1989) and E.P. Stebbing in his book "The Forestry of India" (London, 1921, Vol.1, AJ Reprints Agency, New Delhi, 1982) argued that the colonizers had saved the forests from destruction by indigenous forest users. Stebbing argued that destructive private interests were brought under scientific supervision and control in

the colonial period. The basic edifice of the recent environmental debate over colonialism and Indian forests was laid down by Madhav Gadgil and Ramachandra Guha. They have presented a romanticised notion of human-nature relationship and have agreed upon the fact that in spite of several conflicts between class and caste, there was a harmonious relationship between natural resources and its distribution among the various strata of the society. The authors have termed the period up to 1800 A.D. as 'Golden Age of Equilibrium'.¹ The various levels of claims over the resources were set along the caste lines which initiated a state of equilibrium and provided stability to the supply and demand of resources. Every single caste has their own economic domain and ecological alcove. Their traditional belief systems ensured the conservation of their resource base. While depicting the colonial period, the authors have highlighted the twofold imperial agenda of managing the forest, i.e. profit maximization and exploitation of natural resources. The early environmental debate within the colonial bureaucracy as to whether communities living in proximity to the forests should be allowed their traditional right of access is described at some length. The debate predictably ended with the votaries of people's rights being overruled by those who favoured the sequestering of forests for commercial exploitation and the passing of the draconian Forest Act 1878. Guha has also pointed out to the importance of revenue earning and strategic interests played a major role behind the formulation of the imperialist forest policy. The colonizers completely ignored the indigenous religious practices that ensured regeneration of forests. On the contrary, commercialization of forests ensured complete deforestation.² The technical strategies employed by the forest officials often went against the cultivators. The commercial motives behind the establishment of a state controlled forestry not only disturbed the older land settlement patterns but also ensured the growth of only those species of trees that were commercially valuable. Thus mono cultural forestry was encouraged by destructing the natural bio-diversity. The adverse consequences of the expansion of the railway network and the two world wars on the forests of India have been depicted with great skill. The authors

confirm that due to lack of knowledge about the ecology of tropical forests, the colonial foresters caused huge damage not only by commercial exploitation but also through the faulty conservational methods that were typically termed as ‘scientific’.³

This nationalist interpretation on the destruction of Indian forests has been critically challenged by scholars like Richard Grove, Vinita Damodaran and others. Grove questioned the key assumptions made by Guha. He argued that As the colonial expansion proceeded, the environmental experience of Europeans and indigenous people played a steadily more dominant and dynamic part in the construction of the new European evaluation of nature and in the growing awareness of the destructive impact of European economic activity on the peoples and environments of the ‘newly discovered’ and ‘colonized’ lands.⁴ Systematic forest management and the early notions of conservation were initiated in the colonies only with the ushering of British Imperialism.⁵ He has openly questioned the effectiveness of the communitarian ownership over forests vis-à-vis the British forest policy. It was argued that without exclusionist forest acts and regulations the surviving forms of property management would have been faded away.⁶ The indigenous forest dwellers were primarily held responsible for destruction of forests due to lack of exposure to modern knowledge system. Grove represents conservation as a utilitarian justification for the exploitation of resources. . Though, broader concerns like the drought and desiccationist fear also played their role in the conservation attempts. Grove emphasizes the positive motives of ‘Green Imperialism’ and contends that commitment towards the utilitarian ethos of a section of colonial officers was much more significant than the narrow material interests as upheld by the nationalist scholars on British forestry. Grove negates the idea of any destructive imperial attitude that was harmful to ecology and argues in favour of a rapid ecological transformation which proceeded with the colonial rule.⁷

Scholars like Ravi S. Rajan have focused on the ‘conflict of interest’ that grew between the arable agricultural land and non-arable forests. The chief reason of the conflict was the concern for

revenue appropriation on one hand and the ever increasing demand for timber on the other.⁸ In order to achieve a balance between the two, certain lands were identified to be fit for agriculture while the peripheral and marginal lands were allowed to be developed as forests. The primacy of agriculture over⁹ the forestry was quite evident during the first decades of colonialism. Importance of forestry had a complex notion. Forests were regarded useful for increase in the amount of rainfall, but at the same time forests were seen as a threat to the groundwater reserve as forests sustained themselves on groundwater only.¹⁰

The basic notion of introducing a uniform British Forest Policy all across India have critically been questioned by scholars like K. Shivaramakrishnan. He has pointed out on a series of conflicts over the arable and non-arable lands. Centering his discussion on the introduction of a number of Private Forest Bills between 1865 and 1878 in Bengal¹¹ he tried to explore the conflict of interest over profit maximization and the use of natural resources. It was not only scientific knowledge (deforestation and desiccation) which contributed to the debate but the underplay of various socio economic interests and environmental concerns that gave a debate such a complex character that ultimately the bill could not be formatted.¹²

Another major area of investigation was the introduction of Permanent Settlement and the consequent property rights sanctioned to the Zamindars by the East India Company. In southern Bengal, the forest lands were termed as ‘Jungle Mahal’ hence accepted as private property. Any act to withdraw or curtail the same led to greater resentment.¹³ However, in the forests of Eastern Bengal, a private forest policy was demanded by the EIC officials to cater to the growing demand for wood. This led to a serious controversy as the customary rights of the ‘raiya’ over forests was completely overlooked. Conversion of private forests to protected forest denied the claims of the raiya. The landlords on the other hand were concerned about the degradation of forest cover and soil erosion.¹⁴

Issues like the role of the colonial forest policy in the ecological degradation and the part played by the indigenous communities have been taken up by scholars like Ajay Skaria. He argues that implementation of strict regulations to protect the forests of India was just an extension of the ‘Civilizing Mission’ of the colonizers.¹⁵ Protection of forest was another form of eco-imperialism. The colonial forest officials, trained in the continental forest tradition played the key role in this civilizing mission as mentioned by Skaria. He puts more stress on cultural imperialism rather than economic and commercial considerations. Skaria lamented on the cultural discrimination that the colonizers made by using terms like ‘wild’ and ‘primitive’ to describe the forest tribes.

Some new interpretations came up in the recent years about different environment related issues vis-à-vis the role of the colonial government and the indigenous people. The new genres of writings on India’s Environmental History have received impetus either from Annale School or from Post- Marxian Critical School and have been designated as Post- Colonial Critical scholarship on Environmental History (Sumit Guha, Daud Ali, Aloka Paraser-Sen, Neeledri Bhattacharya, Sajal Nag, Bina Agarwal, Amita Baviskar are some of the few names out of many engaged in such scholarly writings of different areas on forestry India’s Environmental History). A good number of research works has been undertaken on North Western, Central Himalayas and Southern Hills relating environmental issues which include colonial and pre-colonial forestry, forest rights of the indigenous forest people, development and displacement.

Evolution of Forest Legislation in India:

Indian Forest Act of 1865: The first attempt of asserting monopolistic control of the state over the forestry was reflected in the Forest Act of 1865. This act was a direct outcome of the continental forest tradition initiated in colonial Burma by Dietrich

Brandis. This act was primarily passed to acquire those forest areas that were undertaken for the railway supplies.

The Indian Forest Act of 1865 empowered the government of India in the following ways¹⁶:

1. The Government reserved the right to declare any land covered with trees, brushwood or jungle as Government Forests by notification, provided that such notification should not abridge or affect any existing rights of individuals or communities.
2. Local Government may make rules for management and preservation of forests and for regulating the conduct of persons employed on them. Such Rules shall not be repugnant to any law in force.
3. Powers were given to local government to prescribe punishment for breach of provisions of the Act.
4. Rules when confirmed and published had the force of law.

This Act was passed by the Governor General of India in Council and received the assent of the Governor General on 24th February 1865.¹⁷ The most important feature of this Act was that it empowered the local government to draft local rules for their respective provinces for the better management and preservation of the forests. It was aimed at establishing state control over forestry that were required at once, subject to the conditions that existing rights were not abridged.

The Forest Act, 1878: This Act aimed at improving on the inadequacies of the Indian Forest Act of 1865. This act was much more comprehensive in nature. The 1878 Act was just a continuation of the expansionist Imperial Agenda of establishing unusable control over the forests.

Precise Definitions: In the new definitions, 'tree' included palms, bamboo, stumps, brushwood and canes; 'Timber' included trees when they have fallen or have been felled, and all wood, whether

cut up or fashioned or hallowed out for any purpose or not. 'Forest produces included.'¹⁸

a. The following, whether found in, or brought from, a forest or not, that is to say timber, charcoal, caoutchouc, catechu, wood-oil, natural varnish, bark, lac, mahua flowers and myrabolams.

b. The following when found in, or brought from, a forest, that is to say:

1. Trees and leaves, flowers and fruits and all other parts or produce not herein before mentioned of trees.

2. Plants not being trees (including grass, creepers, reeds and moss), and all parts of produce of such plants.

3. Wild animals and skins, tusks, horns, bones, silk cocoons, honey and wax, and all other parts or produce of animals; and tv. Peat, surface soil, rock, and minerals (including limestone laterite, mineral oils and all products of mines or quarries. Besides cattle and rivers were also defined in details.

Classification of Forests: For the first time, forest was classified into three groups namely Reserve forests Protected forest and Village forests. These classifications are contained in the Chapter II section 3-26, chapter III section 27 and chapter IV section 28-33.¹⁹

a) 'Reserved' Forest: In such forests, which were compact and connected to the towns, a legal separation of rights was aimed at. A permanent settlement either extinguished all private rights or transferred them elsewhere or in exceptional circumstances allowed their limited exercise.

b) 'Protected' Forests: These were also controlled by the state. Here the rights were recorded but not settled. The state control was firmly maintained by outlining detailed provisions for the reservation of particular tree species as and when they became

commercially viable and for closing the forests whenever required for grazing and fuel wood collection.

c) 'Village' Forests: The name itself explains this category. Such forests were under the control of the villages and were used by their inhabitants.

The new legislation greatly enhanced the punitive powers of the forest officials and prescribed a comprehensive set of penalties for violation of the act.

Notifications were to be issued for concerned people to record their claims over land and forest produce in the proposed reserved and protected forest. Activities like grazing of cattle and trespassing were prohibited. Provisions were made to impose duties on timber. Certain activities were declared as criminal offences and rigorous imprisonment and fines were imposed to control such 'crime'.

Forest Settlements: Yet another important characteristic of the Forest Act of 1878 was the forest settlement.²⁰ Persons were to be notified to prefer their claim over land and forest produce in any proposed reserved forests. Forest settlement officers were appointed to record such rights and to make some special provision to ensue exercise of such rights. Every person had to appear before the officer, within a fixed period, to register the nature of rights, and the amount and particulars of the compensation claimed in respect thereof. The forest settlement officer was empowered to enter by himself or any officer authorised by him for the purpose, upon any land, and to survey, demarcate and make a map of the same, stop any public or private way or water course in a reserved forest. In the trial of suits, he was given powers of a civil Court. He was also empowered, in the case of a claim to right of pasture or to forest produce, to pass an order admitting or rejecting the same in whole or in part.

The debate over the establishment of colonial control over forests has been categorized under three distinct positions²¹ (a)

Annexationist; (b) Pragmatic; (c) Populist. The Annexationist's claim is the total State Control over all forest areas. Pragmatists argue favouring state controlled governance of technologically valuable forests, while in other areas communal system of management is allowed. The populist claim, on the other, completely rejects state intervention and holds that indigenous forest people must exercise sovereign rights over forests. Between these extreme positions, the colonial Government brought out a comprehensive forest policy in 1894 that clearly spelt out the suzerainty of the colonial interest over that of interest of the commons. Government of India invited Dr. John Augustus Voelker to examine the conditions of agriculture in the country and, how, it could be improved. Subsequently Dr. Voelker submitted his report on improvement of Indian Agriculture in 1893.²²

National Forest Policy Of 1894: The Government of India, came out with a comprehensive forest policy in 1894. It was a clear cut assertion of State's interest over the popular interest. The main features of the Forest Policy 1894²³ are:

1. The maintenance of adequate forests is dictated primarily for the preservation of the climate and physical conditions of the country and to fulfill the needs of the people.
2. Forests which are reservoirs of valuable timber should be managed on commercial lines as a source of revenue to the state.
3. Whenever the effective demand for cultivable land exists and can only be supplied by forest area, the land should ordinarily be relinquished without hesitation, subject to the following conditions:
 - a) Honeycombing of a valuable forest by patches of cultivation should not be allowed; and
 - b) Cultivation must be permanent and must not be allowed to an extent as to encroach upon the minimum area of forest that is

needed to meet the reasonable forest requirement, present and prospective. The following recommendations were made subject to the above mentioned conditions

c) Permanent cultivation should come before forestry

d) The satisfaction of the needs of the local population at non-competitive rates, if not free, should over-ride all consideration of revenue.

e) After the fulfillment of the above conditions the realization of maximum revenue should be the guiding features.

4. The forests were broadly divided into four classes in this policy

a) Forest, the preservation of which was essential on climate or physical grounds.

b) Forest that afforded a supply of valuable timber for commercial purposes

c) Minor forests and

d) Pasture land

These classifications were not intended to be rigid and particular forest might fulfill more than one function. It appears from the policy statement that the forest tracts which supplied valuable timber like teak, *sal* deodar were given greater importance than the minor forests or pastoral land. It presumes that the fourth class of forest referred to as pastures and grazing grounds were only forests in name. They can be conveniently declared as forests in order to obtain statutory settlement.

The essence of the colonial forest policy has been aptly summed up by Elwin (1962) as: “the sole object with which state forests are administered is the public benefit. In some cases the public to be

benefited as the whole body of tax payers, in others, the people of the tract within which the forest is installed; but in almost all cases the contribution and preservation of a forest involve, in greater or lesser degree, the regulation of rights and the restriction of privileges of users in the forest area which may have previously been enjoyed by the inhabitants of its immediate neighbourhood. These regulations and restrictions are justified only when the advantage to be gained by the public is great, and the cardinal principle to be observed is that rights and privileges of individuals must be limited, otherwise for their own benefit, only in such degree as is obviously necessary to secure that advantage.²⁴

Indian Forest Act of 1927: It was the first all-inclusive piece of legislation on colonial forests. This was an attempt to codify all practices of the forest officials and to regulate further people's rights over forest lands and produce. The Forest Act 1927 consolidated the law relating to forests, the transit of forest produce and duty levied on timber and other products. The revenue yielding aspects of forests was given prime emphasis. Under this Act, British Indian forests were reclassified as reserved, protected and village forests. Provisions were made wherein the Forest settlement officer was supposed to record the claims relating to practice of shifting cultivation and to inform the government together with his opinion as to the permissibility or otherwise of the practice. The government was finally to decide on the issue of permission or prohibition. The privilege so granted was always subject to control, restriction and abolition by the Colonial Government.

Basic Features of Indian Forest Act of 1927:

- a) It intensified the power of the state to create reserve forests, village forests and protected forests
- b) Enhanced state control of the timber and non-timber forest produce.
- c) Prescribed penalties for the violation of the act
- d) Formalised the duties and powers of forest bureaucracy.

The concept of 'ecological equilibrium in pre-colonial environmental history of India is based on three broad premises. The first of these focuses on the limited reach of states beyond the agricultural land. Barring a few exceptions, the pre-colonial rulers never participated in the process of natural resource appropriation.²⁵ The second premise talks about the gradual disappearance of the big ancient empires making local forces the prime players. The third premise, while providing a logical corollary to the second, talks about the changing socio economic forces that gave the local communities considerable control over the natural resources within the wider power structure of the village society.²⁶

Conclusion: The colonial state intervention in Indian forests was primarily and basically planned to bring total colonial control over natural resources so that the government could cater the external markets. From all the colonial legislations, it was clear that commercial interests were the primary consideration in declaring forests reserved. The colonial Indian forests had been the central place of strategic raw materials crucial for imperial interest such as timber for shipbuilding, sleepers for the Railways, forest based industries such as pulp, paper and plywood. The colonial forest policy was perceived and chalked out with three dimensional mandate: to organize sustained-yield timber production for the long future; to preserve the forest cover of remote and unstable watersheds; to ensure that the people living in forests have adequate supplies of wood and fodder for their subsistence needs. In reality, however, policy pursued by the colonial government was mostly cantered around the first mandate and the second mandate was pursued to fulfil the first one, however the declared third mandate was never pursued in reality as it directly confronted with the colonial notion of ownership over forests and extraction of forest resources to the maximum extent possible. The most serious consequence of colonial forestry was the diminution of customary rights as well as the decline in traditional conservation and management systems.²⁷

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